

RESIDUAL STRAIN MEASUREMENTS OF GLASS/EPOXY COMPOSITE LAMINATE USING A NEW TYPE OF SPECIMEN DESIGN

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1. Introduction

Residual stresses in fibre composite parts may arise from their manufacturing process and the resultant stress distribution may lead to premature failure of the part. Residual stresses may develop during the curing process and models to predict these stresses have been matured during the past three decades. Some of the first to attempt to model the curing process of fibre composites were Hahn *et al.* [1, 2]. Years later Bogetti [3] and White *et al.* [4, 5] followed with more advanced models. These models included degree of conversion together with temperature dependent material properties which makes these models a coupling of several physical phenomena; structural, thermal, and chemical reaction. Filiou *et al.* [6] applied the Raman spectroscopy technique to assess the residual stress level in a carbon/PEEK composite. Recently, Zhao *et al.* [7] adopted a micro-mechanical approach to study the residual stresses and found that the residual stresses greatly affect the shear failure strength. Ruiz *et al.* [8] conducted an extensive material characterisation to generate material models which were used to predict stresses in a RTM part. Incremental hole drilling was adopted by Sicot *et al.* [9] to investigate the residual stress state in a composite laminate

The topic of this paper relates to residual the stress state in a glass/epoxy composite by measuring the released strains as a through the thickness hole is drilled. The influences from a

few boundary conditions are examined and to accommodate one of the boundary conditions a new residual strain specimen is proposed. To assess the residual stresses, the hole drilling method is applied together with Digital Image Correlation (DIC) to capture the released strains. The purpose of this new type of residual strain specimen is for model validation only.

2. Method

Different specimens are fabricated of Chopped Strand Mat (CSM) E-glass fibres together with an Epoxy matrix. For comparison, a neat Epoxy specimen is made. Extensive details of specimen configurations are given below.

Neat Epoxy specimen (config-1).

The specimen is used as a clarification specimen and will be used to evaluate the suitability of the DIC method for this study. The residual stresses are in addition assessed with photo elasticity. The specimen has the disc shape with a thickness of 2.4mm and a diameter of 60mm. The specimen was made in a silicon mould to minimize boundary restriction as the specimen cures.

CSM E-glass/Epoxy specimen (config-2).

The specimen is cured at room temperature to avoid the effect from the different thermal expansion coefficients between fibre and the epoxy matrix during heating or cooling of the material. Moreover the edge of the specimen is free to contract as a consequence of the

chemical shrinkage. The specimen was made as flat laminate with a thickness of 1.5mm and cut to dimensions of 100x100mm and.

CSM E-glass/Epoxy/Steel ring specimen (config-3).

To impose a nearly fixed boundary condition onto this specimen configuration, a thin steel plate with a 50mm hole in the centre was included in the lamina stacking (cf. Figure-1). The thickness of the steel plate is 1mm and the total thickness of the specimen is 2.1mm. When the epoxy resin gels it will introduce a chemical bond between the glass reinforcement and the steel plate and this will result in residual stress build-up during the curing process. An isothermal curing at 120C for three hours followed by a cooling to room temperature (20C) was chosen to cure the specimen. This led to a fully cured laminate which includes a resin gelation temperature at 120C which introduces tension stresses in the centre region. In addition chemical shrinkage will contribute to tension stresses in this region of the specimen.

Figure 1. Proposed residual stress specimen.

The proposed residual stress specimen (config-3) utilizes a steel plate with a 50mm diameter

hole creating a centre region. The steel plate is placed between two mats of CSM E-glass. Owing to a relatively low thermal expansion coefficient and high stiffness compared to epoxy, the steel washer creates a nearly fixed boundary condition for the central region of the specimen (see Figure 1).

The specimen configurations-2 and -3 are both made with vacuum infusion. To evaluate the residual stresses in the specimens, DIC is used to obtain the released strain field after a 5mm hole has been drilled in the center of the specimen. The Aramis® DIC-system from GOM was used in a single camera setup to obtain the in-plane deformation and strain field. The DIC measuring settings are listed in Table-1.

Table 1. DIC setting are given in the table.

Technique Used	Mono image correlation
Subset size	30x30 pixel
Shift	25 pixel (17% overlap)
Camera	8 bit, 2048 x 2048 ARAMIS 4M system
Field of view	37 x 37 mm
Measurement points	81 x 81
Displacement	
Spatial resolution	0.457 mm / 25 pixel
Resolution	0.1 µm / 0.005 pixel
Strain	
Calculation method	Numerical (3x3 subsets)
Smoothing method	No Smoothing
Spatial resolution	1.37mm
Resolution	55 µm/m

A single camera setup was used to track the in-plane deformations since any out of plane deformations were assumed negligible. A subset size of 30x30 pixels with a shift of 17% was used to capture the strain gradients in vicinity of

RESIDUAL STRESS MEASUREMENTS OF GLASS/EPOXY COMPOSITE LAMINATE USING A NEW TYPE OF SPECIMEN DESIGN

the hole of config-3. Smaller subset sizes were tested but it introduced additional noise and a larger facet size had difficulties in capturing the strain gradients near the hole. The strain field was calculated based on a 3x3 subset grid which is the best available choice in the Aramis® software to capture strain gradients. The noise was determined as a single standard deviation between two images before the hole was drilled (or two images after the hole was drilled). The noise is used to indicate what accuracy that could be expected from the measurements.

3. Theory

An elastic solution for specimen (config-3) of the stress and strain field may be derived analytically or numerically. However in either way the form of the released strain field is presented in a simplified form in Eq-1.

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta\varepsilon_{xx} &= -\Delta\varepsilon_{yy} = Ax^{-2} \text{ for } y = 0 \\ \Delta\varepsilon_{yy} &= -\Delta\varepsilon_{xx} = Ay^{-2} \text{ for } x = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where (A) is coefficient which depend on the elastic constants; Young's Modulus and Poisson Ratio and moreover the imposed stress or strain field.

Figure 2. The elastic solution of specimen (config-3) is plotted and the strain release is symmetric with respect to the x- and y-coordinate axis.

The strain release in vicinity of the hole is captured with DIC and the measurements are presented in the following section.

4. Experimental Results

Drilling the hole in the three specimen configurations was done in a drill press at low rotational speed to secure good drill conditions and to avoid heating of specimens. Drilling in fibre composite material may be challenging and a sharp drill is preferred to avoid fibre rupture (cf. Figure-3) which may lead to faulty measurements of the displacement field and further determine the strains in vicinity of the hole.

Figure 3. The quality of the drilled hole is important for the validity of the DIC data. A common source of error is fibre rupture, which may lead to faulty interpretation of the data.

The released strain field for specimen of config-3 is shown in Figure-4 and similar to Figure-2 it can be seen that the strains decay with distance from the edge of the hole. However a slight asymmetry of the strain field is seen even though the CSM Glass/Epoxy material should yield isotropic properties which should show a symmetric strain field. The measured asymmetry in the strain field was not expected but a proposed hypothesis is a slight anisotropic material behaviour at the length scale of a couple of hole diameters. The data presented in Figure-4 has been subjected to 3x3-averaging filter to smooth out noise. The remaining data

presented in the paper have not been subjected to any filtering.

Figure 4 DIC strain release due to the drilled hole for the composite specimen of config-3. 3x3-averaging filter is used in this figure.

The neat epoxy specimen (config-1) yielded no strain gradient in vicinity of the hole (cf. Figure-5) which indicates that no residual stresses were present in the material as expected.

Figure 5. The normal strains obtained from DIC measurements along the x-axis and y-axis for the neat epoxy specimen (config-1).

The transparent nature of the neat epoxy further made it possible to use its photoelastic

properties and it was verified that the material was stress free after the hole was drilled.

The strain data along the x- and y-axis for the specimen of config-2 is presented in Figure-6. It is similar to the results presented for config-1 seen that no significant strain gradients exist near the hole. This was also expected since the residual stresses in the specimen was minimised when its boundary was not restricted, leaving the specimen to deform freely. In Figure-6 it is however seen that for a positive coordinate a very localised strain gradient is observed for $\epsilon_{yy}(x,y=0)$ and $\epsilon_{yy}(x=0,y)$. This strain gradient is not believed to be associated with residual stresses in the material from its manufacturing process but a consequence of a localised heating of the material during the drilling process.

Figure 6. The normal strains obtained from DIC measurements along the x-axis and y-axis for the neat epoxy specimen (config-2).

The data in Figure-6 seems slightly more spread compared to the data in Figure-5. This could possibly be due to the difference in material but considering the data measured for config-3 (cf. Figure-7) which is less spread, the material difference between config-1 and config-2 does not explain this spread. The spread is however believed to be related to the discrepancy in the quality of speckle pattern. The pattern of config-

RESIDUAL STRESS MEASUREMENTS OF GLASS/EPOXY COMPOSITE LAMINATE USING A NEW TYPE OF SPECIMEN DESIGN

2 was dominated by white areas compared to config-1. Ideally the speckle pattern should be equally mixed between black and white to create unique pattern within each facet. A dominated white or black speckle pattern will decrease the uniqueness of the pattern in a facet and noise in the measurements could be a consequence of this. A solution could be to increase the facet size but this will again reduce the spatial resolution.

For the proposed specimen (config-3) a residual stress state is present and a strain release is measured after the hole has been drilled (cf. Figure-7).

Figure 7. The normal strains obtained from DIC measurements along the x-axis and y-axis for the neat epoxy specimen (config-3).

It is seen that both positive and negative strain gradients in the vicinity of the hole are present. The strain gradients are not completely symmetric around zero and this is proposed to be caused by slight locally anisotropic material behaviour.

The slight asymmetry in the measurements will lead to different residual stress prediction. It is in the following illustrated how the released strains $\epsilon_{xx}(x>0,y=0)$ may be used as an example to predict the residual stress state prior to the hole drilling. The strain data for the remaining

strain components can follow similar approach to make stress predictions.

The strain data of $\epsilon_{xx}(x>0,y=0)$ is used to fit the parameter A in Eq-1. This was done in Matlab® and a R^2 value of 0.922 indicates that a reasonable fit to the data was achieved with the elastic model of Eq-1 (cf. Figure-8).

Figure 8. The elastic solution from Eq-1 may be fitted to the DIC data. The plot only shows the $\epsilon_{xx}(x>0,y=0)$.

Having the model parameter (A) determined a relation between (A) and the residual stress state prior to the hole drilling has to be established.

5. Residual Stress Prediction

The relation was made numerically using the FEA software packages Comsol-Multiphysics®. The FEA model was setup with material properties which previously have been measured for the material constituents.

A sweep of a number of imposed biaxial stress states were analysed for the strain release and converted to the parameter (A) which establish the relation between (A) and the biaxial stress state (σ_0) (cf. Figure-9).

Figure 9. A relation between the factor (A) and the biaxial stress state is established using FEA. The previously determined factor (A) predicts a residual biaxial stress of 12MPa.

Typical values for the uniaxial tension strength for a CSM Glass/Epoxy material have previously been reported in literature to around 120MPa. The biaxial tension strength of the material is by several failure theories predicted to be equal to the uniaxial tension strength or even higher. This will make the influence from the residual stress level less significant to a given biaxial loading of the material. However the influence the residual stress state on the fatigue behaviour still remains an open question.

Conclusion

A new residual stress type specimen configuration for composite material have been proposed and tested. The objective of the specimen is a future model validation of residual stress predictions in composite material due to different curing cycle scenarios.

In addition to the proposed residual stress specimen two additional specimens were tested for the strain release after a hole has been drilled. Two additional specimens showed that no residual stresses were present in the material, when the fixed boundary condition was not present. This confirms that the residual strains

measured are due to curing contraction. All strain release measurements were performed using DIC. The DIC technique further confirmed that it can be used to measure the strain release in combination with the hole-drilling method to assess the residual stress in the material studied.

The proposed residual stress specimen confirmed that stresses were present in the material due to the curing process only and these were quantified by measuring the strain release in vicinity of the hole together with a calibration curve established from an elastic solution generated in the FEA software packages Comsol-multifysics®. The residual stress state were further determined to 12MPa.

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RESIDUAL STRESS MEASUREMENTS OF GLASS/EPOXY COMPOSITE LAMINATE USING A NEW TYPE OF SPECIMEN DESIGN

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